

How the Activities of Oil Multinational Corporations (OMCS) Affect the Health Condition of Rural Coastal People in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined how the activities of Oil Multinational Corporations (OMCS) affect the health condition of rural coastal people in the Niger Delta region. The focus is to provide empirical insight into the fact that the activities of the OMCS generate adverse consequences such as environmental degradation through oil spills and gas flaring among others with adverse consequences for the people. To achieve this broad objective, the study made use of a sample of 1,600 respondents from four (4) states of the Niger Delta region. The sample was using the Taro Yamane formula. The respondents were selected using a multi stage sampling procedure. Thus, relying on the theoretical strength of the World System perspective and analytical models such as the simple percentage as well as the chi-square statistical approaches, the paper out that the activities of the OMCS adversely affect the health condition of the people. However, the most prominent source of these health problems comes from inhaling contaminated air to base on this, the study recommends that the OMCS procedures for all clean-up and remediation should be fully reviewed and over. hauled so as to achieve the expected degree of environmental restoration in line with international best practices.

Keywords: Oil Multinational Corporation, Health Condition, Rural Coastal People, Niger Delta.

Introduction

There are historical evidences showing clearly the problems associated the exploration and exploitation crude deposit by Oil Multinational Companies in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. These problems have received deep-seated attention among indigenous and international agencies as well as scholars across the globe. For nearly sixty-five years today, intensive ecological degradation and the application of detestable legal instruments of subjugation and domination, marginalization, denial and systematical exclusion of the Niger Delta minorities have led to widespread underdevelopment challenges such as adverse health condition, poverty, massive violence and other forms of social ills in the region.

Despite the enormous contribution made by the region to the socio-economic development of Nigeria, there are staggering levels of poverty, hunger and in- deed underdevelopment vis-a-vis when compared to the revenue derived from the natural endowment in the region. Environmental Right Action (ERA, 2008) has reported that the objectives of the Oil Multinational Companies (OMCs) operating in the region appear to be premised on the assumption that profit maximization

is the only basis upon which the company can be run such that any expenditure beyond what is required to get out oil is resisted; that a deal can be made with the state only regardless of the wishes of the local people, that once an agreement has been reached with the state, an oil prospecting company can subdue and intimidate the people of the region as if they are an agency of the state. Inadvertently, this practice has informed the intimidation of the people of the region for a long time now. Again, this adverse social relationship between the state and its multinational allies and the indigenous people of the Niger Delta region became largely antithetical to their traditional values leading to popularly accepted grievance and agitations. This social discontent paved the way for the people to converge on several platforms aimed at articulating their worries and galvanizing themselves for their emancipation. These social platforms led to several consensus such as; of the Ogoni Bill of Rights in 1991, the Kiama Declaration in 1998, the Urhobo Economic Summit in 1998, the South-South Governors.

Declaration for resource control in 2000 and 2011 among others. There is a plethora of literature on the activities of multinational corporations in the Niger Delta Region. The availability of this literature goes a long way to show the magnitude of research interest that has come to characterize the region of late. This is perhaps why Raimi (2017) describes the Niger Delta region and its associated problems as a force of academic gravity. Furthermore, a careful aggregation of the literature into conceptual or subject matter areas reveals more concentration on the discourse on poverty as a result of the activities of MNCS operating in the region.

Enormous financial resources have been derived from oil exploration and exploitation in the region with adverse consequences on the social and physical environment. These adverse consequences range from land degradation, socio economic deterioration to progressive poverty which in turn has propelled high level insecurity and serious health issues in the region. Much as this is the case, the regulatory negligence of the state also provides the enabling environment for oil multinationals to neglect ethical principles and the underlining ethos of corporate social responsibilities attached to the nature of their business, resulting to gross disregard for environmental safety, infrastructural support and human development imperatives.

As mentioned earlier, the link between OMCs and widespread poverty has been a subject of empirical inquiry for several years. Asuni (2009) recounting the understanding of the classical writing of Roxa Luxemburg on the destruction the local economy, made it very clear that one of the key indicators of poverty is the constant destruction of the mainstay of the local economy of the people by multinational company's activities. Aworawo (2000), of OMCs some level of support to the claim, he adduces that when he the activities ate adverse impact on the local environment of tend to the people through generates all kinds of pollution. Hence the implication is that sources of livelihood such as arable land water bodies, forest and mangrove are significantly destroyed. The region under study provides a perfect example of the description provided by the scholars above particularly when destruction of local livelihood is taken into account. This indeed explains why the inhabitants of the area face all manner of socio-economic challenges and are living in poor health conditions that undermine their potential for sustainable development.

The UNEP (2011) in its report states that the Ogoni people located within the study area will be developing respiratory cardiovascular disease and even cancer in years to come. From the foregoing therefore, it is evident that previous studies have contributed to the knowledge in the area of OMCs and poverty in the region. However, very little is still known about the problem in rural coastal communities within the region. It is in light of this, that this study examined the Issue of OMCS, poverty and health challenges in rural coastal areas in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria with particular reference to Etebi, Amassorna, Ubeji and Kula communities.

Research Hypothesis

The more OMCs activities continue to Impact negatively on the environment, the more adverse health conditions of the people will persist in the rural coastal Niger Delta Region.

Review of Related Literature

Oil operations in the Niger Delta Region have been described as a curse rather than a blessing (Turner & Brownhill, 2004). This is largely because the socio-economic cum political upheavals arising from the reactions of the inhabitants of region against the activities of OMCS in the region provides justification for the above position. Interestingly, opinions do not differ about the factors behind the surge of the curse (poverty, conflict and general discontent in the area (Ukeje, 2001). For instance, Naanem, (1995) identified acute scarcity of resource land degradation, water pollution in communities and creation of oil-related Infrastructure such as refineries, fertilizer and petrochemical industries are inevitable outcomes of the increasing expansion of oil production activity in the region. Apart from the intermeddling of the multinationals with the people's traditional and social life, the most devastating is the environmental hazard caused by oil production activities in the area. Oil spillage and gas flaring has destroyed natural resources central to local livelihood.

Before now, Agriculture which was the main stay of the Nigerian economy in the 1960s and 1970s had been significantly abandoned and neglected in preference to high revenue generation from crude oil exploitation. The discovery of oil in commercial quantity was first at Oloibiri in present day Bayelsa state (Shell, 1962). At this point, the state graciously entered into the league of nations who formed the Committee of Crude Oil Producers in 1958 when Shell 'D'Acry, now Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) of Nigeria successfully lifted its maiden export of the product. Since then, Nigeria has become a host to different major oil prospecting companies from the so-called developed countries of the world. Today, crude oil is a major factor in the politics of power both within and outside Nigeria. In order to avoid uninterrupted revenue from oil, the Nigerian state has become subservient to oil multinationals. Agreeably, the Nigerian state is a colonial creation, which by its character tend to function for the interest of foreign capital (jomos & Jin, 2009). This also explains the long-term prospecting right approved for SPDC since the 1930s. Successive leadership of post independent Nigeria have visibly towed the line of the colonial regime by protecting and tilting more towards the demand of foreign capital particularly in the oil sector. Hence, there seem to be little or no political will on the part of government to

change the trend of things for the betterment of the Nigerian citizens especially those in the exploited region where the resource is found.

On several occasions, the state finds it difficult to exercise control over the industries not to talk of enforcing available laws to guide the operations of the oil firms when the state and its functionaries depend on them to survive economically. The fact now remains that Nigeria's political elites who are mostly from non-oil producing regions of the country have continued to maintain their control of state apparatus with which they initiate obnoxious policies which centralizes the economy as first step in asymmetrical distribution (Naanem,1995). The over centralization of socio-political matters in Nigeria is the major challenge for sustainable development in the Niger Delta Region. This hinges on the fact that the central role predisposed geographic unit to uneven and unequal development due to its enormous resources (Larry & Ekundayo, 2017).

Nwankwo and Ifeadi (1988) identified oil spillage, gas flaring, forest destruction, biodiversity loss, effluent discharge and disposal and contamination of sea and (water pollution) as environmental problems associated with oil exploitation in the region. From a social point of view, the implications of oil exploration in the rest is pervasive poverty and underdevelopment, conflict between oil and host companies as well as persistent intra and inter commune munity conflict in the region.

Then the health implication which is the major trust of this paper is pathetic sad scene. To a great extent, disease burdens remain in the Niger Delta region. Preventable and treatable communicable diseases as well as non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are still high and thereby causing rising mortality rate in the area. Most death recorded in the area are associated rising overtly, underdevelopment, malnutrition and mismanagement of the environment of the region. Health care delivery represent a monumental disaster in Nigeria, and the Niger Delta in particular. There is a persistence of poor nutrition and hygiene, limited access to safe water and poor environmental conditions. Health care in the Niger Delta continue to lag behind when compared to other oil rich zones in the world. Many are dying daily for lack of money to afford cheap drugs to treat common curable diseases such as malaria, headache etc.

Emissions from combustion of associated gas (AG) contain toxins, such as benzene nitrogen oxide, dioxins, hydrogen Sulphide, xylene and toluene (Edafienene, 2012). Oil spills and gas flares contaminate surface water, ground water, air, and crops on which the locals depend (Niagu, 2011). Respiratory problems such as asthma and bronchitis, lung disease, heart attack, miscarriage, and skin disease are just some of the reported cases becoming prevalent as a result of exposure to heat from oil exploration related activities (Edafienene, 2012).

Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, this study adopted the World System Theory (WST) developed by Immanuel Wallerstein in his 1974 publication World System Analysis. The WST is any historical social system of interdependent parts that forms a bounded structure and operate according to the distinct rule of a unit with a single division of labour and multiple cultural systems (Wallerstein, 1974).

The theory has the capacity to discuss capitalists activities especially as it relate to exploration and exploitation of rural coastal peripheral nations. In light of this, the theory is adopted here as the analytical framework for this study.

Methodology

The area of the study is the Niger Delta Region (NDR). The NDR is located in the central part of Southern Nigeria. It covers about 70,000 square kilometer of land, about one third of the region is made up of wetlands and it is also a home to the oil industry. All of Nigeria's oil production is carried out in the region. The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive research design. The population of this study consists of all the Niger Delta states. But due to the lack of resources within the reach of the researcher, the study was randomly restricted to four states, the total which includes: Akwa Ibom, Rivers, Delta and Bayelsa Therefore, the total population of the study area is put at 14,906,356 (NPC, 2006). The sample size of the study using the Taro Yamane statistical technique is 400 from each state making it 1,600 respondents on the whole. Multi-stage sampling technique involving the use of purposive, random, stratified and the simple random methods was adopted for the selection of the respondents. Data was collected via the use of primary and secondary sources. For the primary data source, the questionnaire instrument was used, and for the secondary source, information was gathered from written documents. To analyze the data, the simple percentage and chi-square statistical techniques were adopted. The analysis was done based on the number of questionnaires that were collated and this is 1,480.

Results

Fig 1.1 is a column chart describing how the activities of Oil multinationals affect the health condition of rural coastal people. Data presented in the chart shows that 400(27%) of the respondents said drinking polluted water, 967(65.3%) of the respondents said by eating contaminated food resulting from environmental degradation. Then 100 (6.8%) of the respondents said by inhaling polluted air as a result of gas flaring. 13 (0.9%) of the respondents said others.

Test of Hypothesis

The more OMCs continue to impact negatively on the environment, the more adverse health conditions will persist among rural coastal people in the region.

Table 1.1: Chi-square computation for hypothesis

*DF=6; Chi-Square Table value =12.59.; Chi-Square Calculated Value=17.05

Decision rule: Accept null hypothesis if calculated value is less than table value and reject hypothesis if the calculated value is greater than table value. Hence, since the chi-square calculated value of 17.05 as shown in the table above, is higher than the table value of 12.59, it therefore follows that the hypothesis which states that the more OMCs continue to impact negatively on the environment, the more adverse health condition will continue to persist among rural coastal people of the Region.

Discussion

A good number of families in the rural coastal region of the Niger Delta depend on fishing in inland waters as well as offshore. The destruction of fishing and other coastal livelihood activities and the pollution of the area is widely acknowledged by government and non-governmental organizations as one of the major negative outcomes of the activities of oil multinationals.

The findings in this study revealed that the activities of OMCs have serious adverse impact on the health condition of the Niger Delta rural coastal people's adverse impact of the pollution and contamination of food sources in the region due to the activities of the OMCs. Judging from the data in Figure 1.1 above, there is a significant indication that the poor health status of the rural coastal people of the region is directly linked to the unguided operations of OMCs. Also, the data in the same Figure shows that 65.3% of the respondents see contaminated food intake as the dominant source of health hazards of the rural coastal people of the region. This view is supported by Amaize (2012) who found that people who reside in areas where OMCs carry out their operations often complain of health challenges such as respiratory disorder, and skin diseases resulting from bathing polluted water, and even cases of cancers which he adduced has dramatically increased in the region. This is because the rural coastal people have long depended on fishes to meet their protein need, therefore the depletion of protein sources as a result of pollution has brought with it concomitant increase in malnutrition (Ambrose & Ekpu, 1995).

Conclusion

Oil Multinational Companies operating in the region have been identified as the dominant cause of health issues. Finding from the study has shown that respondents have basic knowledge of the activities of OMCs and the attendant environmental consequences such as health hazards, pollution, and degradation usually encountered by the people over the years. Thus, the study concludes that through the negative impacts of the activities of OMCs on the environment, the health condition of the rural coastal dwellers is often jeopardized in many respects.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendation has been preferred. The OMCs procedures for oil clean-up and remediation should be fully reviewed and overhauled so as to achieve the expected degree of environmental restoration in line with international best practices. The Nigerian government and the OMCs operating in the region should partner to provide good healthcare system in the Niger Delta region. However, this should be made affordable and accessible to the less privileged people in the area.

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